

Confidence Interval Coverage of Coefficients in a Multicollinear Logistic Regression Model: A Simulation Study

Sultana Mubarika Rahman Chowdhury and Zoran Bursac
Department of Biostatistics

B.M. Golam Kibria
Department of Mathematics and Statistics

Florida International University
Miami, FL 33199, USA
Corresponding Author Email: schow034@fiu.edu

Abstract: Multicollinearity refers to the condition where two or more independent variables show a strong correlation. Analyzing multicollinear data using generalized linear models (GLM) presents significant challenges. Highly correlated predictors cause the standard error estimates to inflate, resulting in wide confidence intervals, lower predictive power, and less reliable results for the maximum likelihood estimator (MLE) in GLM. Researchers have developed many methods to address the multicollinearity problem. Typically, the performance of various methods is compared based on their mean squared error (MSE). We aim to expand the research in this field for logistic regression (LR), focusing on the confidence intervals based on the Ridge, Liu, and Kibria–Lukman (KL) estimators. A simulation study examined the confidence intervals for estimates based on coverage probability and interval width in logistic regression under various conditions and for a range of shrinkage parameters. This paper is the first in the field to conduct a comparative study based on the coverage probability of confidence intervals in logistic regression.

2. Introduction

Logistic regression is a type of generalized linear model (GLM) that is used in the case of binary response variables. The assumptions of classical linear regression models, such as the dependent variable being continuous and normally distributed with a unit mean and zero variance, are violated in logistic regression. As a result, the ordinary least squares estimation (OLS) procedure that is used for inference in a linear regression setting is not appropriate. Instead, the Maximum Likelihood Estimator (MLE) is preferred as it aligns with the probabilistic framework of logistic regression (Cox, 1958; Hosmer & Lemeshow, 2000; Menard, 2002).

One of the drawbacks of the MLE of β is the effect of the interrelationship of the covariate on the variances of the estimator of β , which may be influential (A. K. M. E. Saleh & Kibria, 2013a). If the predictors are highly correlated, MLE might not always produce reliable results. Highly correlated predictors create a situation commonly known as multicollinearity. It was originally identified by Frisch (1934) in which two or more independent variables show a strong correlation with one another. Analyzing multicollinear data using GLMs involves significant challenges. Highly correlated predictors cause the standard error of these coefficient estimates to inflate, resulting in wide confidence intervals,

lower predictive power, and less reliable results (Schaefer, 1986). Identifying and interpreting significant predictors also becomes difficult (A. Saleh et al., 2019). Additionally, parameter estimation may become unstable and may cause the iterative maximum likelihood estimation algorithm to converge slowly or even fail to converge due to multicollinearity (Hosmer & Lemeshow, 2000).

In the case of logistic regression, there are a number of different approaches to address the multicollinearity problem, much like the ordinary least squares in linear regression. Most of the methods, such as Ridge regression (Hoerl & Kennard, 2000), Lasso regression (Tibshirani, 1996), Liu estimation (Kejian, 1993), Kibria–Lukman estimation (Golam Kibria & Lukman, 2020), that are used in linear regression have been extended to be suitable for logistic regression. Schaefer (1986) extended the linear ridge regression method for binary response variables having correlated predictors. Performances of various logistic ridge regression regularization parameters have been studied by Le Cessiet & Van Houwelingen (1992) and Kibria et al. (2012). A Liu-type estimator was proposed by Inan & Erdogan (2013) with the aim of getting a lower mean square error (MSE) than Schaefer's ridge estimator for logistic regression. An optimal Generalized Logistic Estimator (OGLE) was proposed by Varathan & Wijekoon (2018), which performed better than MLE and some other estimation methods for logistic regression in the presence of multicollinearity. Similarly, numerous studies have been done to propose an effective procedure to deal with multicollinearity in a logistic regression model (Asar et al., 2017; Asar & Genç, 2016; Hoque & Kibria, 2024; Lukman et al., 2020, 2023a; Perez Melo et al., 2024; Phruksawatnon et al., 2021; A. K. M. E. Saleh & Kibria, 2013b; Satoh et al., 2016; Şiray et al., 2015; Urgan & Tez, n.d.). It should be noted that the superiority of any newly proposed shrinkage estimation method compared to others was almost always established based on the performance in terms of MSE. The performance of various shrinkage estimation methods of logistic regression in terms of any other criteria other than MSE has not received much attention in the statistical literature.

In a linear regression setting, Obenchain (1977) first used a confidence region as a criterion to compare ridge regression shrinkage parameters. Different methods of constructing confidence intervals were studied by Vinod (1987), Crivelli et al. (1995), and Chaubey et al. (2018). Revan Özkale & Altuner (2023) in their recent work showed that indicates that both mean interval length and the coverage probability are affected by the choice of the shrinkage parameter for linear ridge regression. Nevertheless, all these works are done mostly for the linear ridge regression method. Thus, our objective is to expand the research in this field for logistic regression for the ridge, Liu, and Kibria–Lukman (KL) estimators. This paper aims to do a comparative study of the methods based on the coverage probability and interval width of the confidence interval (CI) for logistic Ridge, Liu, and KL estimators.

The rest of the paper has been organized as follows: Section 2 describes the theoretical background and methodology of the research, Section 3 explains the simulation procedure, Section 5 discuss the results of the analysis , followed by the concluding remarks on the results in Section 5.

2. Methodology:

2.1 Maximum Likelihood estimator (MLE)

Let us assume there are n observations (X_i, Y_i) , where Y_i are binary dependent variables which are mutually exclusive with π_i probability of $Y_i = 1$ and X_i are p -dimensional rows of covariates. The probability function π_i follows the logistic regression model,

$$\pi_i(X_i) = \frac{\exp(X_i\beta)}{\{1 + \exp(X_i\beta)\}}$$

Here, X_i is the i^{th} row of X , which is an $n \times (p + 1)$ dimensional data matrix, β is a $(p + 1) \times 1$ dimensional vector of coefficients. The log-likelihood function under this model is $l(\beta) = \sum_{i=1}^N y_i \log(\pi_i) + \sum_{i=1}^N (1 - y_i) \log(1 - \pi_i)$. The IRLS algorithm renders an efficient technique to approximate the MLEs by maximizing the log likelihood function by iteratively updating the coefficient estimates:

$$\hat{\beta}_{MLE} = (X' \widehat{W} X)^{-1} (X' \widehat{W} \hat{z})$$

Here, $\widehat{W} = \text{diag} [\hat{\pi}_i(1 - \hat{\pi}_i)]$ and \hat{z} is a vector where the i -th element is, $\hat{z}_i = \log(\hat{\pi}_i) + \frac{y_i - \hat{\pi}_i}{\hat{\pi}_i(1 - \hat{\pi}_i)}$. The MSE of the ML estimator is as follows,

$$MSE(\beta_{ML}^2) = E((\beta_{ML} - \beta)'(\beta_{ML} - \beta)) = \text{tr} \left((X' \widehat{W} X)^{-1} \right) = \sum_{\{j=1\}}^J \frac{1}{\lambda_j}$$

Based on the ML estimator, the Wald test is used to test whether the j -th component of the coefficient vector β is equal to zero, i.e.

$$H_0: \beta_j = 0 \text{ vs } H_1: \beta_j \neq 0$$

$$t_j = \frac{\hat{\beta}_{MLE,j}}{SE(\hat{\beta}_{MLE,j})}$$

Where, $\hat{\beta}_{MLE,j}$ is the j -th element of $\hat{\beta}_{MLE}$ and $S(\hat{\beta}_{MLE,j})$ is the square root of the j -th diagonal element of $\text{Var}(\hat{\beta}_{MLE})$. The variance-covariance matrix of the MLE is calculated in the last step of the iteratively weighted least squares algorithm. Hence, we get the $(1 - \alpha)\%$ confidence interval as,

$$\hat{\beta}_{MLE,j} \pm t_{\frac{\alpha}{2}, n-p} \cdot SE(\hat{\beta}_{MLE,j}).$$

where, $t_{\frac{\alpha}{2}, n-p}$ is the critical value of the student's t-distribution with $n - p$ degrees of freedom.

2.2 Ridge Logistic Regression Estimator (RLoR)

In the presence of multicollinearity, the MSE of the ML estimator gets inflated, similar to OLS. Schaefer et al. (1984) proposed a logistic ridge regression model in such cases. The estimator is as follows,

$$\hat{\beta}_{RR} = (X'WX + kI_p)^{-1} X'WX \hat{\beta}_{MLE} \quad : k > 0.$$

where k is known as the shrinkage parameter. The MSE of the above estimator becomes,

$$MSE(\beta_{RR}^2) = E((\beta_{RR} - \beta)'(\beta_{RR} - \beta)) = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^J \lambda_j}{(\lambda_j + k)^2} + k^2 \sum_j \frac{\alpha_j}{(\lambda_j + k)^2}$$

The variance-covariance matrix of $\hat{\beta}_{RR}$ is obtained as follows,

$$Var(\hat{\beta}_{RR}) = F_k Var(\hat{\beta}_{MLE}) F_k'$$

Where, $F_k' = (X'WX + kI_p)^{-1} X'WX$

The following t-test statistic was used by Halawa & El Bassiouni (2000) to test whether the i -th component of the parameter vector is significant,

$$t_j = \frac{\hat{\beta}_{RR,j}}{SE(\hat{\beta}_{RR,j})}$$

where, $\hat{\beta}_{RR,j}$ is the j -th element of $\hat{\beta}_{RR}$ and $S(\hat{\beta}_{RR,j})$ is the square root of the j -th diagonal element of $Var(\hat{\beta}_{RR})$. The above test statistics are assumed to be asymptotically normally distributed with mean 0 and unit variance (Cule et al., 2011; Halawa & El Bassiouni, 2000) under the null hypothesis. The 95% confidence interval of the test statistic is,

$$\hat{\beta}_{RR,j} \pm t_{\frac{\alpha}{2}, n-p} \cdot SE(\hat{\beta}_{RR,j}),$$

where, $t_{\frac{\alpha}{2}, n-p}$ is the critical value of the student's t-distribution with $n - p$ degrees of freedom. The formula to calculate the shrinkage parameter k has been proposed by numerous researchers. In this paper, we have chosen 27 ridge regression parameters from the literature that were proven to perform better than MLE in terms of MSE. Additionally, based on the research, we have also proposed 8 new shrinkage parameters (K27 -K35) based

on the best performing ones among the first 27 parameters. The list of all the ridge regression parameters is given in Table 1.

Table 1: Shrinkage Estimators (Ridge)

No	Author	Estimator
1	Hocking et al., 1976	$k_1 = \frac{\hat{\sigma}^2 \sum (\hat{\alpha}_j^2 \lambda_j^2)}{(\sum (\hat{\alpha}_j^2 \lambda_j))^2}$
2	Hoerl & Kennard, 1976	$k_2 = \frac{\hat{\sigma}^2}{\max(\hat{\alpha}^2)}$
3	Thisted, 1976	$k_3 = \frac{(p-2)\hat{\sigma}^2}{(\sum_{j=1}^p \hat{\beta}_j)^2}$
4	Hoerl & Kennard, 1976	$k_4 = \frac{p\hat{\sigma}^2}{\sum_{j=1}^p (\hat{\alpha}_j^2)}$
5	Golam Kibria, 2003	$k_5 = \text{median} \left(\frac{\hat{\sigma}^2}{\hat{\alpha}_j^2} \right)$
6	Khalaf & Shukur, 2005	$k_6 = \frac{\lambda_{\max} \hat{\sigma}^2}{(n-p)\hat{\sigma}^2 + \hat{\lambda}_{\max} \hat{\alpha}_{\max}^2}$
7	Alkhamisi et al., 2006	$m_j = \frac{\lambda_j \hat{\sigma}^2}{(n-p)\hat{\sigma}^2 + \lambda_j \hat{\alpha}_j^2}$ $k_7 = \max(m_j)$
8	Schaffer, 1984	$k_8 = \frac{1}{\hat{\alpha}_{\max}^2}$
9	Asar et al., 2014	$k_9 = \frac{p^2 \hat{\sigma}^2}{\lambda_{\max}^2 \sum_{j=1}^p (\hat{\alpha}_j^2)}$
10	Asar et al., 2014)	$k_{10} = \frac{p^3 \hat{\sigma}^2}{\lambda_{\max}^3 \sum_{j=1}^p (\hat{\alpha}_j^2)}$
11	Asar et al., 2014	$k_{11} = \frac{p \hat{\sigma}^2}{\lambda_{\max}^{\frac{1}{3}} \sum_{j=1}^p (\hat{\alpha}_j^2)}$
12	Asar et al., 2014	$k_{12} = \frac{p^2 \hat{\sigma}^2}{(\sum_{j=1}^p \sqrt{\lambda})^{\frac{1}{3}} \sum_{j=1}^p (\hat{\alpha}_j^2)}$
13	Nomura, 1988	$k_{13} = \frac{p \hat{\sigma}^2}{\sum_{j=1}^p \left(\frac{\hat{\alpha}_j^2}{1 + \left(1 + \lambda \sqrt{\frac{\hat{\alpha}_j^2}{\hat{\sigma}^2}} \right)} \right)}$

JSM 2025 – Biometrics Section

14	Dorugade, 2014	$k_{14} = \text{median} \left(\frac{2\hat{\sigma}^2}{\lambda_{\max} \hat{\alpha}_j^2} \right)$
15	Dorugade (Dorugade, 2014)	$k_{15} = \text{harmonic mean} \left(\frac{2\hat{\sigma}^2}{\lambda_{\max} \hat{\alpha}_j^2} \right)$
16	Dorugade (Dorugade, 2014)	$k_{16} = \text{geometric mean} \left(\frac{2\hat{\sigma}^2}{\lambda_{\max} \hat{\alpha}_j^2} \right)$
17	Feras and Gore (2009)	$k_{17} = \frac{p\hat{\sigma}^2}{\sum_{j=1}^p \hat{\alpha}_j^2 / \{(\hat{\alpha}_j^2 \lambda_j^2 / 4\hat{\sigma}^2 + 6\hat{\alpha}_j^2 \lambda_j^2 / 4\hat{\sigma}^2)^2 - \hat{\alpha}_j^2 \lambda_j^2 / 4\hat{\sigma}^2\}}$
18	Lukman & Ayindez (2017)	$k_{18} = \max \left(\frac{\hat{\sigma}^2}{\lambda_j \hat{\alpha}_j^2} \right)$
19	Lukman et al. (2017)	$k_{19} = \text{median} \left(\frac{2\hat{\sigma}^2}{\lambda_{\max} \hat{\alpha}_j^2} \right)$
20	Lukman & Ayindez, (2017)	$k_{20} = \text{median} \left(\frac{1}{\frac{2\hat{\sigma}^2}{\lambda_{\max} \hat{\alpha}_j^2}} \right)$
21	Lukman et al. 2018	$k_{21} = \sqrt{1/p \sum_{j=1}^p \frac{\lambda_j \hat{\sigma}^2}{(n-p)\hat{\sigma}^2 + \lambda_{\max} \hat{\alpha}_j^2}}$
22	Lukman et al. 2018	$k_{22} = \sqrt{p \sum_{j=1}^p \frac{\lambda_{\max} \hat{\sigma}^2}{(n-p)\hat{\sigma}^2 + \lambda_j \hat{\alpha}_j^2}}$
23	Lukman et al. 2018	$k_{23} = \text{Median} \left(\sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^p \frac{\lambda_{\max} \hat{\sigma}^2}{(n-p)\hat{\sigma}^2 + \lambda_j \hat{\alpha}_j^2}} \right)$
24	Muniz and Kibria 2009	$k_{24} = \left(\prod_{j=1}^p \frac{\lambda_j \hat{\sigma}^2}{(n-p)\hat{\sigma}^2 + \lambda_j \hat{\alpha}_j^2} \right)^{1/p}$
25	Lukman et al 2018	$k_{25} = \text{Max} \left(\sqrt{\frac{\lambda_{\max} \hat{\sigma}^2}{(n-p)\hat{\sigma}^2 + \lambda_j \hat{\alpha}_{\max}^2}} \right)$
26	Lukman et al., 2023a	$k_{26} = \min \left(\frac{1}{\hat{\alpha}_j^2} \right)$
27	Lukman et al., 2023a	$k_{27} = \left(\frac{p}{\sum_{j=1}^p \hat{\alpha}_j^2} \right)$
28	Proposed	K28 = mean(k23, k24, k25)
29	Proposed	K29 = mean(k21, k22)
30	Proposed	K30 = harmonic.mean(k23, k24, k25)
31	Proposed	K31 = geometric.mean(k23, k24, k25)
32	Proposed	K32 = harmonic.mean(k21, k22)
33	Proposed	K33 = geometric.mean(k21, k22)
34	Proposed	K34 = mean(k25, k26)
35	Proposed	K35 = mean(k26, k27)

2.3 Liu Logistic regression estimator (LLoR)

The Liu estimator for logistic regression, as discussed by (Månsson & Shukur, 2011; Urgan & Tez, n.d.) and rooted in the work of (Kejian, 1993), has been demonstrated to effectively reduce the high mean square error associated with the maximum likelihood estimator (MLE) in the presence of multicollinearity. It is defined as:

$$\hat{\beta}_{Liu} = (X'WX + I_p)^{-1}(X'WX + dI_p)\hat{\beta}_{MLE} \quad : 0 \leq d \leq 1.$$

where d is a biasing parameter. The variance-covariance matrix of $\hat{\beta}_{Liu}$ is,

$$Var(\hat{\beta}_{Liu}) = F_d Var(\hat{\beta}_{MLE}) F_d'$$

where $F_d = (X'WX + I_p)^{-1}(X'WX + dI_p)$

Students - t statistic has been used for Liu logistic regression estimator in the literature by (Halawa & El Bassiouni, 2000; Imdadullah et al., n.d.) to test the significance of estimators.

$$t_j = \frac{\hat{\beta}_{Liu,j}}{SE(\hat{\beta}_{Liu,j})}$$

where, $\hat{\beta}_{Liu,j}$ is the *j*- th component of the parameter of $\hat{\beta}_{Liu}$, and $SE(\hat{\beta}_{Liu,j})$ is the square root of the variance-covariance matrix. The confidence interval hence, is as follows,

$$\hat{\beta}_{Liu,j} \pm t_{\frac{\alpha}{2},n-p} \cdot SE(\hat{\beta}_{Liu,j}),$$

where, $t_{\frac{\alpha}{2},n-p}$ is the critical value of the student's t-distribution with *n – p* degrees of freedom. Table 2 below shows the list of 14 biasing parameters that were selected from the literature based on their MSE performances.

Table 2: List Shrinkage Parameters (Liu)

No	Author	Estimator
1	Golam Kibria et al., 2011	$D1 = \max \left(0, \frac{\hat{\alpha}_{max}^2 - \widehat{\sigma}^2}{\frac{1}{\lambda_{max}} + \hat{\alpha}_{max}^2} \right)$
2	Golam Kibria et al., 2011	$D2 = \max \left(0, \text{median} \left(\frac{\hat{\alpha}_j^2 - \widehat{\sigma}^2}{\frac{1}{\lambda_j} + \hat{\alpha}_j^2} \right) \right)$
3	Golam Kibria et al., 2011	$D3 = \max \left(0, \text{mean} \left(\frac{\hat{\alpha}_j^2 - \widehat{\sigma}^2}{\frac{1}{\lambda_j} + \hat{\alpha}_j^2} \right) \right)$
4	Månsson et al., 2012	$D4 = \max \left(0, \max \left(\frac{\hat{\alpha}_j^2 - \widehat{\sigma}^2}{\frac{1}{\lambda_j} + \hat{\alpha}_j^2} \right) \right)$

5	Shukur et al., 2015	$D5 = \max \left(0, \min \left(\frac{\hat{\alpha}_j^2 - \widehat{\sigma}^2}{\frac{1}{\lambda_j} + \hat{\alpha}_j^2} \right) \right)$
6	Shukur et al., 2015	$D6 = \max \left(0, \text{median} (q_j) \right) \quad \text{where } q_j = \frac{\hat{\alpha}_j^2 - 1}{\max(\frac{1}{\lambda_j}) + \hat{\alpha}_j^2}$
7	Shukur et al., 2015	$D7 = \max \left(0, \text{mean} (q_j) \right)$
8	Shukur et al., 2015	$D8 = \max \left(0, \max (q_j) \right)$
9	Shukur et al., 2015	$D9 = \max \left(0, \min (q_j) \right)$
10	Qasim et al., 2020	$D10 = \max \left(0, \text{median} \left(\frac{\hat{\alpha}_j^2 - \widehat{\sigma}^2}{\max(\frac{\widehat{\sigma}^2}{\lambda_j}) + \hat{\alpha}_{max}^2} \right) \right)$
11	Qasim et al., 2020	$D11 = \max \left(0, \text{mean} \left(\frac{\hat{\alpha}_j^2 - \widehat{\sigma}^2}{\max(\frac{\widehat{\sigma}^2}{\lambda_j}) + \hat{\alpha}_{max}^2} \right) \right)$
12	Qasim et al., 2020	$D12 = \max \left(0, \max \left(\frac{\hat{\alpha}_j^2 - \widehat{\sigma}^2}{\max(\frac{\widehat{\sigma}^2}{\lambda_j}) + \hat{\alpha}_{max}^2} \right) \right)$
13	Qasim et al., 2020	$D13 = \max \left(0, \min \left(\frac{\hat{\alpha}_j^2 - \widehat{\sigma}^2}{\max(\frac{\widehat{\sigma}^2}{\lambda_j}) + \hat{\alpha}_{max}^2} \right) \right)$
14	Lukman et al., 2023a	$D14 = \min \left(\frac{\hat{\alpha}_j^2}{\frac{1}{\lambda_j} + \hat{\alpha}_j^2} \right)$

2.4 Kibria-Lukman Logistic regression estimator (KLLoR)

In case of multicollinearity issue on linear regression, (Kibria & Lukman, 2020) proposed an estimator which was later expanded in case of logistic regression by Lukman et al.(2023). The estimator is written as,

$$\hat{\beta}_{KL} = (X'WX + kI_p)^{-1}(X'WX - kI_p) \widehat{\beta}_{MLE} = W(k)M(k) \hat{\beta}_{MLE}; 0 < k < 1.$$

where, k is the shrinkage parameter. Hence the variance-covariance matrix of $\hat{\beta}_{KL}$ is written as,

$$Var(\hat{\beta}_{KL}) = W(k)M(k)Var(\hat{\beta}_{MLE})M^{-1}(k)W^{-1}(k)$$

The test statistic based on the Kibria-Lukman estimator is as follows:

$$t_j = \frac{\hat{\beta}_{KL,j}}{SE(\hat{\beta}_{KL,j})}$$

Where $\hat{\beta}_{KL,j}$ is the j -th component of the parameter of $\hat{\beta}_{KL}$, and $\widehat{SE}(\hat{\beta}_{KL,j})$ is the standard error.

The $(1-\alpha)$ % confidence interval is,

$$\hat{\beta}_{KL,j} \pm t_{\frac{\alpha}{2}, n-p} \cdot SE(\hat{\beta}_{KL,j})$$

where, $t_{\frac{\alpha}{2}, n-p}$ is the critical value of the student's t-distribution with $n - p$ degrees of freedom. The Kibria Lukman shrinkage parameters applied in this paper are listed in Table 3. Additionally, we have tried 6 new shrinkage parameters in the case of Kibria – Lukman estimators with an aim to find the best performing parameter estimator for confidence interval coverage.

Table 3: Shrinkage parameters (Kibria – Lukman)

No	Author	Shrinkage parameter
1	Kibria & Lukman, 2020	$kl1 = \min \left[\frac{\widehat{\sigma}^2}{2\widehat{\alpha}_j^2 + \widehat{\sigma}^2/\lambda_j} \right]$
2	Kibria & Lukman, 2020	$kl2 = \text{harmonic. mean} \left[\frac{\widehat{\sigma}^2}{2\widehat{\alpha}_j^2 + \widehat{\sigma}^2/\lambda_j} \right]$
3	Lukman et al., 2023a	$kl3 = \min \left(\frac{1}{\widehat{\alpha}^2} \right)$
4	Golam Kibria & Lukman, 2020	$kl4 = \min \left(\frac{\lambda_j}{1 + 2\lambda_j\widehat{\alpha}_j^2} \right)$
5	Proposed	$kl5 = \max \left[\frac{\widehat{\sigma}^2}{2\widehat{\alpha}_j^2 + \widehat{\sigma}^2/\lambda_j} \right]$
6	Proposed	$kl6 = \text{mean} \left[\frac{\widehat{\sigma}^2}{2\widehat{\alpha}_j^2 + \widehat{\sigma}^2/\lambda_j} \right]$
7	Proposed	$kl7 = \text{median} \left[\frac{\widehat{\sigma}^2}{2\widehat{\alpha}_j^2 + \widehat{\sigma}^2/\lambda_j} \right]$
8	Proposed	$kl8 = \sqrt{\min \left[\frac{\widehat{\sigma}^2}{2\widehat{\alpha}_j^2 + \widehat{\sigma}^2/\lambda_j} \right]}$

9	Proposed	$kl9 = \sqrt{\text{median} \left[\frac{\widehat{\sigma}^2}{2\widehat{\alpha}_j^2 + \widehat{\sigma}^2/\lambda_j} \right]}$
10	Proposed	$kl10 = \sqrt{\text{mean} \left[\frac{\widehat{\sigma}^2}{2\widehat{\alpha}_j^2 + \widehat{\sigma}^2/\lambda_j} \right]}$

2.5 Performance Criterion

Coverage probability (CP), confidence interval width (CIW), and the mean square error (MSE) as the performance criteria for the study. The aim was to identify the shrinkage parameter that gives a high CP with a narrow CI, indicating greater precision. Coverage probability of the pth predictor is basically the probability that the estimated confidence interval consists of the true parameter. CIW is calculated for the pth predictor by subtracting the lower CI from the upper CI. To calculate the MSE following formula was used,

$$MSE(\hat{\beta}) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{j=1}^N (\hat{\beta}_j - \beta)' (\hat{\beta}_j - \beta)$$

Where, $\hat{\beta}_j$ is the estimate of the true parameter β , and N is the number of replications. $(\hat{\beta}_j - \beta)$ represents the difference between the estimated and true parameter vectors at the j^{th} replication. The next section explains the simulation procedure conducted for the comparative analysis.

3. Simulation Study:

A Monte Carlo Simulation procedure was carried out individually for various tuning parameters of the Ridge (35), Liu (14), and Kibria-Lukman estimators (10). The simulation was conducted for sample sizes $n = 100, 200, 300$, correlation levels $\rho = 0.6, 0.8, 0.85, 0.90, 0.95, 0.99$, and number of predictors $p = 2, 4, 6$ for 5000 iterations. The correlated predictors are generated by following the method of (McDonald & Galarneau, 1975) as follows,

$$x_{ij} = (1 - \rho^2)^{1/2} w_{ij} + \rho w_{i(p+1)}, \quad j = 1, \dots, p, \quad i = 1, \dots, n$$

here, w_{ij} is the error term ρ is the correlation between two predictors, p is the number of explanatory variables, and n is the number of samples. Eigen values $(\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_p)$ and the corresponding eigen vectors of the matrix $\mathbf{X}'\mathbf{X}$ are computed. The response variable y_i is generated from a Bernoulli distribution, i.e, $y_i \sim Be(\pi_i)$, where $\pi_i = \frac{\exp(x_i'\beta)}{1 + \exp(x_i'\beta)}$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$. The average of the MSE and CIW has been calculated over the 5000 iterations, and the CP is calculated by dividing the number of times the true parameter falls inside the confidence interval by the number of iterations. The simulation procedure has been carried out using the R programming language version 4.5.1. The detailed simulation results can be made available upon request to the authors.

4. Results and Discussion

Overall, the simulation results indicate that while MLE consistently achieves the nominal 95% coverage across all conditions, this comes at the expense of higher MSE and wider

confidence intervals. Biasing methods like Ridge, Liu, and Kibria Lukman were able to reduce the MSE substantially, but in most cases, fail to maintain the coverage. The goal of this analysis was to identify the shrinkage parameters that give at least the nominal 95% CP while maintaining a narrow confidence interval compared to MLE, regardless of the simulation conditions. Thereby, we calculated the average coverage probability and average confidence interval widths across all sample sizes, number of covariates, and correlation levels. Tables 4 and 5 give the average coverage probability and average CIW across all conditions for Ridge, Liu, and Kibria–Lukman shrinkage parameters.

Table 4: Average Coverage Probability across all conditions

Ridge Parameters	Average coverage	Ridge Parameters	Average Coverage
MLE	0.952	k31	0.932
k1	0.598	k32	0.939
k2	0.731	k33	0.933
k3	0.748	k34	0.939
k4	0.641	K35	0.644
k5	0.407	Liu Parameters	
k6	0.730	d1	0.850
k7	0.407	d2	0.749
k8	0.733	d3	0.728
k9	0.729	d4	0.828
k10	0.714	d5	0.728
k11	0.680	d6	0.776
k12	0.520	d7	0.783
k13	0.532	d8	0.829
k14	0.461	d9	0.728
k15	0.670	d10	0.776
k16	0.488	d11	0.786
k17	0.648	d12	0.828
k18	0.033	d13	0.728
k19	0.167	d14	0.809
k20	0.951	Kibria-Lukman parameters	
k21	0.946	k1	0.938
k22	0.898	k2	0.936
k23	0.913	k3	0.939
k24	0.929	k4	0.938
k25	0.939	k5	0.944
k26	0.644	k6	0.942
k27	0.733	k7	0.938
k28	0.913	k8	0.939
K29	0.946	k9	0.942
k30	0.935	k10	0.943

Table 5: Average Confidence Interval width across all conditions

Ridge Parameters	average CI width	Ridge Parameters	Average CI width
MLE	26.873	k31	4.463
k1	1.689	k32	4.314
k2	3.182	k33	3.437
k3	8.537	k34	4.167
k4	1.592	K35	1.621
k5	0.641	Liu Parameters	
k6	12.323	d1	18.350
k7	0.641	d2	2.048
k8	3.248	d3	1.193
k9	3.919	d4	7.117
k10	3.748	d5	1.187
k11	2.142	d6	2.350
k12	0.866	d7	2.782
k13	0.957	d8	7.144
k14	1.069	d9	1.185
k15	2.518	d10	2.115
k16	0.870	d11	2.703
k17	1.397	d12	7.008
k18	0.080	d13	1.185
k19	0.241	d14	1.939
k20	6.300	Kibria-Lukman parameters	
k21	5.793	k1	10.401
k22	2.189	k2	15.965
k23	4.268	k3	21.321
k24	5.416	k4	10.278
k25	4.167	k5	26.151
k26	1.621	k6	25.157
k27	3.248	k7	17.743
k28	4.268	k8	22.705
K29	5.793	k9	24.011
k30	4.823	k10	25.402

The results from Tables 4 and 5 can be better visualized in Figure 1. Here in Figure 1 here we can see the Average Coverage probability, average confidence interval weight, and MSE of the shrinkage parameters that had an average coverage over 90%.

Figure 1: Average Coverage Probability, Average CI width, and Average MSE

From the results, it can be seen that only a few Ridge and Kibria Lukman shrinkage parameters had a higher coverage than 90% and none of the liu estimators made the cutoff.

The key findings from the simulation can be listed as below,

- Compared to MLE, the shrinkage estimators show a comparatively small increase in MSE under multicollinearity for the Ridge, Liu and Kibria Lukman estimators.
- However, most of the shrinkage estimators that have smaller MSE do not show consistent coverage and fail to maintain a nominal coverage probability of 95%.
- Only a few of the Ridge and Kibria–Lukman shrinkage parameter estimators could maintain a coverage probability above 93%.
- On average Liu shrinkage parameters covered here had very low coverage probability.

Among the shrinkage parameters that maintain a consistent coverage probability of 95%, **k20** proposed by Lukman & Ayindez (2017) had the narrowest confidence interval on average under most of the conditions. Therefore, it can be recommended for confidence interval inferences among the shrinkage parameters studied.

5. Concluding remarks

In this paper, we have done an extensive comparative study of a number of Ridge, Liu, and Kibria-Lukman shrinkage parameters with the aim to gain insight into their performances on confidence interval coverage. In this paper, we have chosen 27 Ridge, 14 Liu, and 4

Kibria–Lukman shrinkage parameters from the literature that were proven to perform better than MLE in terms of MSE. Additionally, based on the research, we have also proposed 8 new ridge shrinkage parameters and 6 new Kibria–Lukman shrinkage parameters based on their performances. We have calculated their average coverage probability, confidence interval width, and MSE across all conditions considered in order to investigate their consistency in performance for different criteria. The simulation results indicated that the nominal 95% coverage probability was continuously maintained using MLE, but this stability came at the price of larger confidence intervals and greater MSE. Ridge, Liu, and Kibria-Lukman estimators, on the other hand, typically showed reduced MSE, although several were unable to maintain sufficient coverage. While the Liu estimators continuously performed poorly in terms of coverage, only a small number of Ridge and Kibria-Lukman parameters were able to attain the nominal coverage. Of the shrinkage parameters that were assessed, the most advantageous balance was shown by the estimator put out by Lukman and Ayinde (2017), which maintained nominal 95% coverage with relatively lower confidence intervals across the majority of situations. Considering the results, it is crucial to keep in mind that selecting shrinkage parameters based on their MSE performance may raise the risk of making a type 1 error if the research's objective is to make inferences using the multicollinear logistic regression model's confidence interval.

References:

- Alkhamisi, M., Khalaf, G., & Shukur, G. (2006). Some modifications for choosing ridge parameters. *Communications in Statistics-Theory and Methods*, 35(11), 2005–2020.
- Asar, Y., Arashi, M., & Wu, J. (2017). Restricted ridge estimator in the logistic regression model. *Communications in Statistics: Simulation and Computation*, 46(8), 6538–6544. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03610918.2016.1206932>
- Asar, Y., & Genç, A. (2016). New Shrinkage Parameters for the Liu-type Logistic Estimators. *Communications in Statistics - Simulation and Computation*, 45(3), 1094–1103. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03610918.2014.995815>
- Asar, Y., Karabrahimoğlu, A., & Genç, A. (2014). Modified ridge regression parameters: a comparative Monte Carlo study. *Hacettepe Journal of Mathematics and Statistics*, 43(5), 827–841.
- Chaubey, Y. P., Khurana, M., & Chandra, S. (2018). Confidence intervals based on resampling methods using ridge estimator in linear regression model. *New Trends in Mathematical Sciences*, 6(4).
- Cox, D. R. (1958). The regression analysis of binary sequences. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society. Series B (Methodological)*, 20(2), 215–242.
- Crivelli, A., Firinguetti, L., Montano, R., & Munóz, M. (1995). Confidence intervals in ridge regression by bootstrapping the dependent variable: a simulation study. *Communications in Statistics-Simulation and Computation*, 24(3), 631–652.
- Cule, E., Vineis, P., & De Iorio, M. (2011). Significance testing in ridge regression for genetic data. *BMC Bioinformatics*, 12, 1–15.
- Dorugade, A. V. (2014). New ridge parameters for ridge regression. *Journal of the Association of Arab Universities for Basic and Applied Sciences*, 15, 94–99.
- Frisch, R. (1934). *Statistical confluence analysis by means of complete regression systems*.
- Golam Kibria, B. M. (2003). Performance of some New Ridge regression estimators. *Communications in Statistics Part B: Simulation and Computation*, 32(2), 419–435. <https://doi.org/10.1081/SAC-120017499>
- Golam Kibria, B. M., & Lukman, A. F. (2020). A new ridge-type estimator for the linear regression model: Simulations and applications. *Scientifica*, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2020/9758378>

- Golam Kibria, B. M., Månsson, K., & Shukur, G. (2011). *CESIS Electronic Working Paper Series A Ridge Regression estimator for the zero-inflated Poisson model A Ridge Regression estimator for the zero-inflated Poisson model*. <http://www.cesis.se>
- Halawa, A. M., & El Bassiouni, M. Y. (2000). Tests of regression coefficients under ridge regression models. *Journal of Statistical Computation and Simulation*, 65(1–4), 341–356.
- Hocking, R. R., Speed, F. M., & Lynn, M. J. (1976). A class of biased estimators in linear regression. *Technometrics*, 18(4), 425–437.
- Hoerl, A. E., & Kennard, R. W. (1976). Ridge regression iterative estimation of the biasing parameter. *Communications in Statistics-Theory and Methods*, 5(1), 77–88.
- Hoerl, A. E., & Kennard, R. W. (2000). Ridge regression: Biased estimation for nonorthogonal problems. *Technometrics*, 42(1), 80–86. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00401706.2000.10485983>
- Hoque, M. A., & Kibria, B. M. G. (2024). Performance of some estimators for the multicollinear logistic regression model: theory, simulation, and applications. *Research in Statistics*, 2(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/27684520.2024.2364747>
- Hosmer, D. W., & Lemeshow, S. (2000). *Applied Logistic Regression* (2nd ed.). John Wiley & Sons. <https://doi.org/10.1002/0471722146>
- Imdadullah, M., Aslam, M., & Altaf, S. (n.d.). *liureg: A Comprehensive R Package for the Liu Estimation of Linear Regression Model with Collinear Regressors*.
- Inan, D., & Erdogan, B. E. (2013). Liu-type logistic estimator. *Communications in Statistics: Simulation and Computation*, 42(7), 1578–1586. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03610918.2012.667480>
- Kejian, L. (1993). A new class of biased estimate in linear regression. *Communications in Statistics - Theory and Methods*, 22(2), 393–402. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03610929308831027>
- Khalaf, G., & Shukur, G. (2005). Choosing ridge parameter for regression problems. *Communication in Statistics-Theory and Methods*, 34(5), 1177–1182.
- Kibria, B. M. G., & Lukman, A. F. (2020). A new ridge-type estimator for the linear regression model: simulations and applications. *Scientifica*, 2020(1), 9758378.
- Kibria, B. M. G., Månsson, K., & Shukur, G. (2012). Performance of Some Logistic Ridge Regression Estimators. *Computational Economics*, 40(4), 401–414. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10614-011-9275-x>
- Le Cessiet, S., & Van Houwelingen, J. C. (1992). Ridge Estimators in Logistic Regression. In *Appl Statist* (Vol. 41, Issue 1).
- Lukman, A. F., & Ayindez, K. (2017). Review and classifications of the ridge parameter estimation techniques. In *Hacettepe Journal of Mathematics and Statistics* (Vol. 46, Issue 5, pp. 953–968). Hacettepe University. <https://doi.org/10.15672/HJMS.201815671>
- Lukman, A. F., Emmanuel, A., Clement, O. A., & Ayinde, K. (2020). A Modified Ridge-Type Logistic Estimator. *Iranian Journal of Science and Technology, Transaction A: Science*, 44(2), 437–443. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40995-020-00845-z>
- Lukman, A. F., Kibria, B. M. G., Nziku, C. K., Amin, M., Adewuyi, E. T., & Farghali, R. (2023a). K-L Estimator: Dealing with Multicollinearity in the Logistic Regression Model. *Mathematics*, 11(2). <https://doi.org/10.3390/math11020340>
- Lukman, A. F., Kibria, B. M. G., Nziku, C. K., Amin, M., Adewuyi, E. T., & Farghali, R. (2023b). K-L Estimator: Dealing with Multicollinearity in the Logistic Regression Model. *Mathematics*, 11(2). <https://doi.org/10.3390/math11020340>
- Månsson, K., Kibria, B. M. G., & Shukur, G. (2012). On Liu estimators for the logit regression model. *Economic Modelling*, 29(4), 1483–1488. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.econmod.2011.11.015>
- Månsson, K., & Shukur, G. (2011). A Poisson ridge regression estimator. *Economic Modelling*, 28(4), 1475–1481. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.econmod.2011.02.030>
- McDonald, G. C., & Galarnau, D. I. (1975). A Monte Carlo evaluation of some ridge-type estimators. *Journal of the American Statistical Association*, 70(350), 407–416.
- Menard, S. (2002). *Applied Logistic Regression Analysis* (Vol. 106). SAGE Publications. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781412983433>
- Nomura, M. (1988). On the almost unbiased ridge regression estimator. *Communications in Statistics-Simulation and Computation*, 17(3), 729–743.
- Obenchain, R. L. (1977). Classical f-tests and confidence regions for ridge regression. *Technometrics*, 19(4), 429–439.

JSM 2025 – Biometrics Section

- Perez Melo, S., Bursac, Z., & Golam Kibria, B. M. (2024). Comparison of Test Statistics for Testing the Regression Coefficients in the Ridge, Liu and Kibria-Lukman Logistic Regression Models: Simulation and Application. *International Journal of Statistics and Probability*, 13(3), 48. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ijsp.v13n3p48>
- Phruksawatnon, P., Jitthavech, J., & Lorchirachoonkul, V. (2021). Determining the optimal ridge parameter in logistic regression. *Communications in Statistics: Simulation and Computation*, 50(11), 3569–3580. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03610918.2019.1626890>
- Qasim, M., Amin, M., & Omer, T. (2020). Performance of some new Liu parameters for the linear regression model. *Communications in Statistics - Theory and Methods*, 49(17), 4178–4196. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03610926.2019.1595654>
- Revan Özkale, M., & Altuner, H. (2023). Bootstrap confidence interval of ridge regression in linear regression model: A comparative study via a simulation study. *Communications in Statistics - Theory and Methods*, 52(20), 7405–7441. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03610926.2022.2045024>
- Saleh, A., Arashi, M., & Kibria, B. M. G. (2019). *Theory of Ridge Regression Estimation with Applications*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Saleh, A. K. M. E., & Kibria, B. M. G. (2013a). Improved ridge regression estimators for the logistic regression model. *Computational Statistics*, 28(6), 2519–2558. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00180-013-0417-6>
- Saleh, A. K. M. E., & Kibria, B. M. G. (2013b). Improved ridge regression estimators for the logistic regression model. *Computational Statistics*, 28(6), 2519–2558. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00180-013-0417-6>
- Satoh, K., Tonda, T., & Izumi, S. (2016). Logistic regression model for survival time analysis using time-varying coefficients. *American Journal of Mathematical and Management Sciences*, 35(4), 353–360. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01966324.2016.1215945>
- Schaefer, R. L. (1986). Alternative Estimators in Logistic Regression when the Data are Collinear. *Journal of Statistical Computation and Simulation*, 25(1–2), 75–91. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00949658608810925>
- Schaefer, R. L., Roi, L. D., & Wolfe, R. A. (1984). A Ridge Logistic Estimator. *Communications in Statistics - Theory and Methods*, 13(1), 99–113. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03610928408828664>
- Schaffer, S. (1984). Higher order multigrid methods. *Mathematics of Computation*, 43(167), 89–115.
- Shukur, G., Månsson, K., & Sjölander, P. (2015). Developing Interaction Shrinkage Parameters for the Liu Estimator — with an Application to the Electricity Retail Market. *Computational Economics*, 46(4), 539–550. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10614-014-9458-3>
- Şiray, G. Ü., Toker, S., & Kaçiranlar, S. (2015). On the restricted liu estimator in the logistic regression model. *Communications in Statistics: Simulation and Computation*, 44(1), 217–232. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03610918.2013.771742>
- Thisted, R. A. (1976). *Ridge Regression, Minimax Estimation, and Empirical Bayes Methods*. Stanford University. <https://books.google.com/books?id=QPz6nQEACAAJ>
- Tibshirani, R. (1996). Regression shrinkage and selection via the Lasso. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society Series B: Statistical Methodology*, 58(1), 267–288.
- Urgan, N. N., & Tez, M. (n.d.). *LIU ESTIMATOR IN LOGISTIC REGRESSION WHEN THE DATA ARE COLLINEAR*.
- Varathan, N., & Wijekoon, P. (2018). Optimal generalized logistic estimator. *Communications in Statistics - Theory and Methods*, 47(2), 463–474. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03610926.2017.1307406>
- Vinod, H. D. (1987). Confidence intervals for ridge regression parameters. In *Time Series and Econometric Modelling: Advances in the Statistical Sciences: Festschrift in Honor of Professor VM Joshi's 70th Birthday, Volume III* (pp. 279–300).